

InterAcción y Perspectiv

Revista de Trabajo Social

ISSN 2244-808X
D.L. pp 201002Z43506

Julio-Diciembre 2023

Vol. 13 No. 2

Universidad del Zulia
Facultad de Ciencias Jurídicas y Políticas
Centro de Investigaciones en Trabajo Social

Interacción y Perspectiva
Revista de Trabajo Social
Vol. 13 N°2 203-215 pp.
Julio-diciembre

Dep. Legal pp 201002Z43506
ISSN 2244-808X
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ARTÍCULO DE INVESTIGACIÓN

Disonancia cognitiva en la psicología de la producción del discurso profesional de los gerentes /DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7812192

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Resumen

El artículo determina que una de las principales habilidades para convertirse en gerente como especialista es el dominio del discurso profesional. Asegura el desarrollo de la cooperación y el entendimiento mutuo entre colegas, socios, gerentes y subordinados. El discurso profesional es una herramienta obligatoria para un gerente a la hora de administrar trabajadores y establecer relaciones comerciales. El discurso profesional determina el uso de términos profesionales que corresponden a las especificidades de la actividad gerencial y las particularidades de la industria de la gestión. La investigación realizada averiguó el grado de uso de los términos profesionales en el discurso profesional a partir de la posición de cada rol desempeñado por cada grupo de directivos (nivel superior, medio, inferior) en el proceso de desempeño de sus funciones oficiales. Se descubrió la relación entre el grado de uso de términos profesionales en comunicación y el nivel de gestión al que pertenece el encuestado. Reveló una disonancia entre el uso de términos profesionales y su percepción. El análisis mostró que cuanto más bajo es el nivel de gestión, más negativamente los gerentes perciben los términos profesionales en el discurso profesional. Al mismo tiempo, el nivel de uso de términos profesionales es muy alto en todos los grupos de directivos. Uno manifestó su insatisfacción con el nivel de habilidades profesionales del habla adquiridas en las instituciones de educación superior. Por lo tanto, los futuros gerentes deben dominar las habilidades profesionales del habla en una institución de educación superior.

Palabras clave: discurso profesional, gerente, disonancia cognitiva, términos profesionales, habilidades del habla profesional.

Recibido: 19/01/2023 Aceptado:15/03/2023

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Abstract

Cognitive dissonance in the psychology of managers professional speech

The article determines that one of the main skills of becoming a manager as a specialist is the mastery of professional speech. It ensures the development of cooperation and mutual understanding between colleagues, partners, managers and subordinates. Professional speech is a mandatory tool for a manager when managing workers and establishing business relationships. Professional speech determines the use of professional terms that correspond to the specifics of managerial activity and the particularities of the management industry. It discovered the relationship between the degree of the use of professional terms in communication and the level of management to which the respondent belongs. One revealed a dissonance between the use of professional terms and their perception. The analysis showed that the lower the level of management, the more negatively managers perceive professional terms in professional speech. At the same time, the level of the use of professional terms is very high in all groups of managers. One subject revealed dissatisfaction with the level of professional speech skills acquired at higher education institutions. Therefore, future managers should master professional speech skills at a higher education institution.

Key words: professional speech, manager, cognitive dissonance, professional terms, professional speech skills.

1.- Introduction

Professional communication takes place between representatives of a certain professional community. It allows them to easily understand a received professional message and all aspects of the activity inherent in this particular field of specialization.

Professional speech as one of the tools of professional competence is of particular interest. It is this tool that formalizes the information intended to be conveyed by interlocutors during professional speech into speech patterns and written symbols.

Therefore, one of the main skills of becoming a manager is mastering professional speech. It ensures the development of cooperation and mutual understanding between colleagues, partners, managers and subordinates. Professional speech is a mandatory tool of a manager when managing workers and establishing professional communication.

The formation of a manager as a specialist is based on his/her psychological and personal qualities and the mastery of professional skills. One of these skills is professional speech. Professional speech of managers requires the acquisition of professional knowledge and skills in accordance with the chosen specialization, in other words, it requires the acquisition of professional speech competence.

The study of the psychological aspect of producing professional speech will allow finding out the particularities of the manager's provision and perception of

professional information in Ukraine from the perspective of thinking, feelings, and the ability of the individual.

2.- Literature review

The relevance of the analysis of the psychology of producing professional speech is argued by the focus of scientific papers that reveal: the essence of professional speech (Haupt, 2016); features of professional speech (Komulainen, et al., 2019), features of professional speech evaluation (Stratulat, Martina, Tretiak, Hordiichuk, Boieva & Shvetsova, 2021), features of various types of professional speech (Duijm, Schoonen & Hulstijn, 2018), the use of information technologies in mastering professional speech (Zinchenko, Romanukha, Revutska, Cheverdak, 2020), features of speech activity of certain types of managers' activities (McAlevy, Rhiart, 2019), features of strategies for various types of professional speech (Anthony & Garner, 2016; Orwig, 2020; Vettorel, 2019).

Research by Kotter (1982) shows that most general managers spend 70% to 90% of their working time in communication with other people. Hunt (1999) believes that about 80% of manager's working time is devoted to communication, but he uses this time to listen. In the process of listening, one collects information and makes an appropriate decision, or encourages other individuals to make a decision. Sidorenko's research (2008, p. 44), "directors spend 60% to 64% of their working time on direct or indirect communication." Large-scale studies by Porter and Noria (2018) on managing manager's time showed that at the meeting, the manager spends about 72% of the working time.

Particularities of the psychology of producing professional speech by managers in Ukraine have not been studied before. This issue is particularly relevant because the management profession is quite popular. In addition, this issue is gaining relevance because of a large number of applicants studying this specialty at higher education institutions of Ukraine. The analysis of this aspect of the manager's professional activity will allow us to determine the place of this issue in the average activity of an ordinary manager. Besides, it will provide an opportunity to focus on certain aspects of the speech process. This, in turn, will make it possible to increase the level of professional speech competence of the individual in the process of learning and in further professional activities.

The purpose of the article is to conduct a study that will allow determining the specific weight of working time spent by Ukrainian managers on professional speech, the level of use and psychological perception of professional terms, and the need to master professional speech skills by future managers at a higher education institution.

3.- Research methods

The research was conducted using the author's questionnaire. The questionnaire contained only closed questions. Conducting the research was based on the respondents' use of the reflection method allowing individuals to realize the motives of their own actions, their condition, and evaluate their own actions.

Managers of different management levels and different economic branches of Ukraine participated in the study. 232 people took part in the survey. The key criterion for the selection of respondents, whose answers were taken for further processing, was practical management experience of more than 1 year. This criterion is the main one

because experience is the result of numerous interactions of an individual with the environment, his/her cognitive response to the existing situation. Experience is gained only by repeatedly performing certain actions. We defined experience as the main criterion, as it is the primary source of individual's knowledge, and only employees who have experience in a certain activity can analyze it. 176 managers met this criterion.

After the collection of primary information using the questionnaire, individual information was transferred into aggregate using manual and machine processing methods. The analysis of the received information was carried out using statistical methods, which allows us to establish correlations of certain factors.

4.- Research results

As defined by Iacocca (1990, p. 68), "Management is nothing but setting people to work. The only way to set people up for vigorous activity is to communicate with them."

Avramenko, Yakovenko, Shiyka (2015, p. 5) believe, "Mastering the culture of business communication contributes to the establishment and development of cooperation and partnership relations between colleagues, managers and subordinates, partners and competitors, largely determining their (relationship) effectiveness."

Professional speech is a necessary tool for managing an organization. According to Tarasov (1973, p. 37), "The very fact that human behavior can be controlled using language is a truism and requires neither extensive proof nor even demonstration of examples."

Professional speech of managers is determined by the specifics of business communication. As noted by Koltunova (2000, p. 5): "The specificity of business communication is that the collision, interaction of economic interests and social regulation is carried out within the legal framework".

According to Baeva (2001, p. 8, 9), "business communication is a type of interpersonal communication aimed at achieving some objective agreement." She notes that the main feature of business communication is that we "have to communicate with those we need." In addition, "the specificity of business communication leads to the opinion that it should be learned", "this is necessary for successful business contact requiring the ability to interact with a partner: overcoming barriers in communication, taking the necessary psychological position, reaching the appropriate level of communication, etc."

At the same time, "the information transmitted must be accurate and clear... as well as professionally correct." (Ilyin, 2017, p. 7)

Therefore, in professional speech, it is mandatory to use professional terms that correspond to the specifics of managerial activity and the particularities of the management industry.

According to Sidorenko's research (2008), on average, 34% of working time is spent on a direct dialogue with people; about 12% of working time on phone conversations; about 17% of working time on e-mail correspondence.

Large-scale studies by Porter and Noria (2018) on managing manager's time showed that approximately half (47%) of the work of CEOs took place in the company's office. The rest of their work took place while visiting other company

locations, meeting with external entities, commuting, traveling and at home. At the same time, 61% of time was spent on personal interaction; 15% accounted for telephone negotiations and written correspondence; 24% of time was spent on electronic communications. The analysis of interactions showed that one-on-one meetings were the most common (on average, they accounted for 42% of managers' meetings); they are followed by meetings with two to five participants (21%). The analysis of the duration of business conversations showed that meetings up to 15 minutes account for 7% of all meetings, about 30 minutes - 23%; about 1 hour - 32%, 1-2 hours - 21%, 2-5 hours - 13%, more than 5 hours - 4%. The studies of these and many other scientists confirm the need for a manager to master speech skills and show that the acquisition of professional speech skills is a prerequisite for becoming a professional manager.

Higher education in the chosen management field provides an opportunity to gain knowledge and master the necessary skills for the best performance of one's professional duties. The discovery of such prerequisites among the managers studied led to the analysis of their level of education (see Table 1).

Table 1.
The highest level of education of respondents in the management field or other field of education

The highest level of education in the management field	Managers, work experience of more than 1 year		Managers, work experience less than 1 year	
	Quantity (n)	%	Quantity (n)	%
Higher (in management)	64	36	38	68
Higher (in other areas)	109	62	14	25
Professional and technical	3	2	4	7
Overall average	0	0	0	0
Total	176	100	56	100

Source: Authors development

The research findings show that the largest part of the respondents who have professional education in management are those who have less than 1 year of experience as a manager (68%). Only 36% of the respondents with work experience of more than 1 year received higher education in management. We believe that such a difference in education is based on the fact that the majority of managers without experience are young people who purposefully received higher education in this field, and other respondents who have been working in the position for more than a year have higher education in another field and gained management experience through practice.

The analysis of the respondents, by the level of the position held (see Fig. 1), shows that the majority of the respondents (56%) are lower level managers, managers of the technical level of management (operational managers). This level of management coordinates the work of direct operational executors and ensures day-to-

day, standardized operations and activities necessary for the ongoing operation of the organization.

Mid-level managers are one-third of all respondents (32%). This level includes heads of a department or a large division. This level of management ensures the coordination of the work of structural divisions of the organization and deals with the development and implementation of the operational plans of the organization in accordance with the decisions of top managers.

Fig. 1.
Distribution of respondents by the level of the position held

Source: Authors development

The third group of respondents (12%) are top-level managers of the organization, namely: heads of the organization, presidents, members of supervisory boards, etc. These managers are responsible for the definition of the mission and goals of the organization in order to ensure a long-term development strategy and adaptation to the factors of the external environment (Mikhno, Koval, Ternavskyi, 2020). The analysis of the amount of time a manager spends on professional speech (see Table 2) shows that according to 35% of the respondents, they spend from 61% to 80% of their working time on communication; 37% of the interviewed managers spend from 41% to 60% of their working time on business communication; other respondents (23%) spend less than 41% of their working time on business communication. These data differ from previous studies by other scientists due to the difference in the object of research. Our object of research includes managers of all levels of management. Previous studies analyzed the performance of top-level managers.

Table 2
Amount of working hours per day spent by the manager on professional speech

Amount of time	Quantity (n)	%
Less than 20% of working time	5	3
From 22% to 40% of working time	35	20
From 41% to 60% of working time	66	38
From 61% to 80% of working time	62	35
More than 81% of working time	8	5
Total	176	100

Source: Authors development

However, you can trace a certain trend if you rank these data according to the criteria of the manager's belonging to a certain level of management (see Table 3). The analysis of these data shows that with regard to top-level managers, the general results of previous studies by other authors correspond to the results of our study.

Table 3.
Amount of working hours per day spent by managers at different management levels on professional speech

Amount of time	Lower level managers		Middle level managers		Upper level managers	
	Quantity(n)	%	Quantity (n)	%	Quantity (n)	%
Less than 20% of working time	5	5				
From 22% to 40% of working time	35	35				
From 41% to 60% of working time	47	47	19	34		
From 61% to 80% of working time	12	12	37	66	13	62
More than 81% of working time					8	38
Total	99	100	56	100	21	100

Source: Authors development

Almost one-third of senior managers (38%) spend more than 81% of their working time on professional speech, and the rest (62%) spend between 61% and 80% of their working time on it.

The situation with mid-level managers is different. Most middle level managers (66%), like top-level managers, spend 61% to 80% of their working time on professional speech, and only one-third (34%) of respondents at this management level spend 41% to 60% on it.

The analysis of managers at the lower management level shows completely different results. Only 12% of the lower level managers spend 61% to 80% of their working time on professional speech. The majority of respondents of this management level (48%) spend 41% to 60% of their working time communicating on business matters. More than one-third of managers (40%) spend less than 40% of their working time on professional speech. This tendency is caused by the fact that managers of this management level usually spend most of their working time supervising the work of subordinates and solving current issues that do not require communication.

The results of the analysis of these data indicate that the higher the level of management of managers, the greater part of working time is spent on professional speech.

Professional speech of managers determines the use of professional terms that correspond to the specifics of managerial activity and the particularities of the management industry. We believe that professional speech is a process of exchanging messages in a certain field of knowledge using appropriate professional terms, while the process involves employees who, due to the implementation of this process, fulfill their official duties.

Professional terms are words or phrases that are "characteristic of the speech of people of a certain profession", "which denotes the concept of a certain field of knowledge or human activity" and "clearly and unambiguously denotes a scientific or special concept". (Yuriev, 2016; Bantash et al., 2020)

The analysis of the speech activity of managers revealed that none of the managers noted that they did not use professional terms. Therefore, it can be concluded that all of them use professional speech in the course of their activities.

The activity of the organization determines the distribution of manager's social roles within the organization: Subordinate-Manager, Colleague-Colleague, Manager-Subordinate.

The conducted research reflects the degree of the use of professional terms in business professional speech. It defines the level of the use of professional terms from the position of each social role performed by each group of managers (higher, middle, lower level) in the process of performing their official duties (Kostetska et al., 2021).

From the position of the Subordinate-Manager role, managers often use professional terms and rarely use exclusively professional terms (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2.
Use of professional terms in professional speech with executives

Source: Authors development

Results on the use of professional terms differ by groups of managers. The results show that the higher the level of management, the more professional terms are used in business communication with executives.

The analysis of the use of professional terms in the process of business communication with colleagues shows that the majority of managers (from 79% to 86%) often use professional terms during business communication with their colleagues. (see Fig. 3)

Fig. 3.
Use of professional terms in professional speech with colleagues

Source: Authors development

At the same time, the higher the level of the manager's position, the more often he/she uses professional terms in professional speech with colleagues.

The analysis of the use of professional terms in the process of professional speech with subordinates shows that only managers of the highest management level use exclusively professional terms in communication with subordinates. (see Fig. 4)

The majority of managers often use professional terms when communicating with subordinates (from 76% to 80%). However, unlike top-level managers, middle- and lower-level managers sometimes use professional terms (from 20% to 21%).

Based on this, we can conclude that the higher the level of management, the higher the level of the use of professional terms in professional speech with subordinates.

Fig. 4.
Use of professional terms in professional speech with subordinates

Source: Authors development

The analysis shows that the higher the level of management at the organization, the higher the level of the use of professional terms in all types of professional speech: with executives, with colleagues, with subordinates. Perception of a message is a psychological phenomenon of interpretation of external and internal signals, reflection of objects and environmental phenomena. It has a subjective nature and depends on the experience and knowledge of the individual. The analysis of the psychological perception of the message with the large amount of professional terms (see Table 4) indicates a partially positive attitude of managers to this type of information.

Table 4.
The attitude of managers to information with the large amount of professional terms

Reaction to received information	Lower level managers		Middle level managers		Upper level managers	
	Quantity(n)	%	Quantity(n)	%	Quantity(n)	%
Very positive (I would like to use this one)	6	6	15	27	15	71
Partially positive (I would like more information in plain language)	90	91	41	73	6	29
Negative (I would like the information to be provided in plain language)	3	3				
Total	99	100	56	100	21	100

Source: Authors development

At the same time, the lower the level of the manager's position, the more negatively he/she relates to the perception of professional terms in business communication.

The result of comparing the use of professional terms with the psychological perception of information with the large number of professional terms indicates cognitive dissonance of perception. On the one hand, the majority of managers (from 76% to 88%) often use professional terms in business communication, while the majority of managers (from 29% to 91%) have a partially positive attitude to messages that contain the large amount of professional information. They believe that more information should be provided in plain language.

Especially significant cognitive dissonance can be seen at the middle and lower levels of management. Mid-level managers often use professional terms in business communication with executives, colleagues and subordinates (from 80% to 88%), while 73% of the respondents have problems with psychological perception of messages with the large number of professional terms and wish to receive more information in plain language.

Lower level managers often use professional terms in their activities (from 79% to 88%), while 91% of the respondents would like to receive more information in plain language, and 3% would like to receive all information without professional terms.

Thus, there is a cognitive dissonance between the existing speech acts of the individual and the perception of information from the perspective of business,

professional communication. The manager's professional activity requires a set of competencies: general competencies; special competencies; psychological and personal competencies. These competences are directly influenced by professional speech competence, which should be mastered by the individual during professional training.

The conducted research determined the level of satisfaction with business communication skills acquired as part of higher education. Satisfaction with the level of professional business speech skills and skills of using professional terms in the process of business speech appeared to be satisfactory. (see Fig. 5)

Fig. 5.
Satisfaction with the level of professional speech skills obtained in the process of acquiring higher education

Source: Authors development

Satisfaction with the level of acquired relevant skills is very low: 97% of the respondents are not satisfied with the level of professional speech skills and 88% with the level of skills of using professional terms.

This indicates the need to improve the methodology and the process of mastering professional speech skills when learning the specialty at higher education institutions.

5.- Conclusions

The results of the analysis of the managers' survey show that the higher the level of management control, the greater part of the working time is spent on professional speech. Professional terms are used in the process of professional speech. The analysis of managers' activities has revealed that the higher the level of management, the more professional terms are used in professional speech. The analysis of the psychological perception of messages with a large amount of

professional terms indicates a partially positive attitude of managers to this type of information. At the same time, the lower the level of the manager's position, the more negative the perception of professional terms in professional speech. Thus, in the professional speech of managers, there is a cognitive dissonance between the existing speech acts of the individual and his/her psychological perception of information messages. Satisfaction with the level of professional speech skills acquired in the process of obtaining higher education by profession is very low. Given the direct impact of professional speech on the manager's professional competence, we consider it necessary to introduce the mastery of professional speech and acquisition of professional and speech competence in higher education in the management specialty.

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